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Organizational Citizenship Behavior, Organizational Climate, and Employee Performance

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Abstract

This study investigates the impact of organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) and climate (OC) on employee performance. The population used contains employees working in one of the pharmaceutical companies in Cimahi, West Java, where their sum is 1,533 people. By the Slovin formula with a margin of error of 10%, the sum of samples needed is 94. Furthermore, they are picked up by the simple random sampling method. The structural equation model based on partial least square is utilized to analyze the data because of the sample size. After testing hypotheses and discussing the facts, this research infers that OCB has no effect on employee performance, but OC does with a positive sign.

Keywords: Pharmaceutical Company, Employee Achievement, Working Atmosphere

INTRODUCTION

To persist in the rivalry, a company needs to utilize its unique resources to achieve a competitive advantage (Madhani, 2009), such as technology and people (Ardana, Mujiati, & Utama, 2012). Furthermore, Ardana et al. (2012) explain that people are the resource that can follow the change in era; therefore, they need to get training and development as an asset. All of these things carried out by the company are to improve their working performance (Lestari & Ghaby, 2018).

Some antecedents of working performance exist. At least two determinants can be available. The first is organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) (Chiang & Hsieh, 2012; Wu, You, Fu, & Tian, 2014; Basu, Pradhan, & Tewari, 2016; Abrar & Isyanto, 2019; Barsulai, Makopondo, & Fwaya, 2019; Lestari & Ghaby, 2018). The second is the organizational climate (OC) (Agyemang, 2013; Bhat, 2014; Bhat & Bashir, 2016; Raja, Madhavi, & Sankar, 2019; Obeng, Quansah, Cobbinah, & Danso, 2020). However, it is still found research showing that OCB does not influence employee performance (Agustiningih, Thoyib, Hadiwidjojo, & Noermijati, 2016) and neither does OC (Pasaribu & Indrawati, 2016).

This research intends to examine the OCB and OC effect on employee performance based on these opposing facts utilizing one of the pharmaceutical companies in Cimahi, West Java. This company produces drugs so that it must pay attention to the quality of work of the employees. This quality is the reflection of employee performance.

Theoretically, OCB refers to the employee's willingness to work beyond their job depiction (Schermerhorn Jr., Hunt, Osborn, & Uhl-Bien, 2010). Employees with high OCB will do everything without the expectation of obtaining financial rewards. They are ready to work voluntarily to meet their company goals (Organ, 1988). Therefore, they will outperform in the workplace (Robbins & Judge, 2018). In their research, Chiang & Hsieh (2012) and Wu et al. (2014) prove a positive impact of OCB on employee performance. Correspondingly, Basu et al. (2016), Abrar & Isyanto (2019), Barsulai et al. (2019), and Lestari & Ghaby (2018) confirm the same result.

Academically, the working atmosphere reflects a combination of employee perception about the desired working and social environment. The leaders can renew this climate to create employee satisfaction by surveying their opinion (Higgins, 1982). Hence, employees working in a comfortable environment tend to perform a good result. In their study, Agyemang (2013), Bhat (2014), Bhat & Bashir (2016), Raja et al. (2019), and Obeng et al. (2020) affirm this statement by revealing the positive effect of climate in the workplace on employee performance.

By considering these supporting facts about the effect of OCB and organizational climate on employee performance, two hypotheses can be stated in this manner.

H₁. The positive influence of OCB on employee performance happens.

H₂. The positive influence of organizational climate on employee performance happens.

II. RESEARCH METHOD

2.1. Variable Definition

The variables utilized consist of two kinds. Firstly, the dependent variable: employee performance. Adopting Thompson (2005), this study uses four items. Moreover, these items are displayed in Table 1 and measured by an interval scale, ranging from 1 for strongly disagree until 5 for strongly agree.

Table 1. The items of employee performance

Items	Scale
I can set the working-based targets (EP1)	Interval
I can reach the targets well (EP2)	Interval
I can allocate the time well in the workplace (EP3)	Interval
I can accomplish works beyond the target (EP4)	Interval

Source: Thompson (2005)

Secondly, the independent variables consist of organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) and organizational climate (OC). According to Hoofman, Blair, Meriac, & Woehr (2007), OCB has five dimensions. They are altruism, conscientiousness, sportsmanship, courtesy, and civic virtue. In this study, the OCB dimension items are based on Lin, Lyau, Tsai, Chen, & Chiu (2010), as seen in Table 2. Furthermore, these items are measured by an interval scale, ranging from 1 for strongly disagree until 5 for strongly agree.

Table 2. The items of OCB dimensions

Dimension	Items	Scale
Altruism	I assist my unattended co-workers (ALT1).	Interval
	I assist my co-workers having weighty loads (ALT2).	
	I assist new co-workers even though my help is not needed (ALT3).	
	I assist my co-workers with work issues (ALT4).	
Conscientiousness	I reduce the personal chat with my co-workers during work (CONS1).	Interval
	I reduce the involvement of unrelated chat with works (CONS2).	
	I can come to the workplace early if the situation requires me to do it (CONS3).	
	I can follow the instructions without supervision (CONS4).	
Sportsmanship	I do not complain about unimportant substances (SPORT1).	Interval
	I give attention to the right things (SPORT2).	
	I tend to calm (SPORT3).	
	I do not search for the organization's mistakes (SPORT4).	
Courtesy	I attempt to create working harmony at work (COURT1).	Interval
	I consider the consequence of my actions on co-workers (COURT2).	
	I voluntarily attend the meeting in the workplace (COURT3).	
	I like to organize a meeting in the workplace (COURT4).	

Table 2. The items of OCB dimensions

Dimension	Items	Scale
Civic virtue	I am present in the unimportant meetings that can increase a corporate image (CV1). I keep following the variation in the organization (CV2). I read and follow notes and publications at the workplace (CV3). I give a chance to assess the best for the organization (CV4).	Interval

Source: Lin et al. (2010)

- b. Indicating Mutonyi, Slåtten & Lien (2020), this study utilizes eight items to measure organizational climate. Likewise, these items are measured by an interval scale, ranging from 1 for strongly disagree until 5 for strongly agree, and present in Table 3.

Table 3. The items of organizational climate

Items	Scale
My supervisor allocates the responsibility to me (OC1).	Interval
My supervisor induces me to perform initiative (OC2).	Interval
My supervisor is ready to listen to me (OC3).	Interval
Employees have a chance to solve similar issues through various methods (OC4).	Interval
Tolerance to do faults is given in my workplace (OC5).	Interval
I can study something new in the workplace (OC6).	Interval
I can obtain to learn a new method to finish my work (OC7).	Interval
I can get knowledge when demanding it (OC8).	Interval

Source: Thompson (2005)

2.2. The method to take samples and get the data

The total population (N) of the employees working at the company in this study is 1,533. Moreover, this study applies the Slovin formula in the first equation to count the sample size (n).

$$n = \frac{N}{N(e)^2+1} \dots\dots\dots \text{(Equation 1)}$$

By exhausting a margin of error (e) of 10%, the sample size $(n) = \frac{1.533}{1.533(10\%)^2+1} = \frac{1.533}{16,33} = 93.87 \approx 94$ employees.

After getting this number, this study utilizes simple random sampling to take samples from the population. Once 94 employee names are known, the next step is surveying online to obtain the data. This process happens from 16 until 30 September 2019. In this process, Hartono (2012) explains the questionnaire distribution is essential to capture the responses.

The responses of employees have to meet validity and reliability testing (Ghozali, 2016). Hence, the confirmatory factor analysis and composite reliability analysis are employed to attain that condition (Ghozali 2008).

- For the validity test, if the item loading factor exceeds 0.5, the item is declared valid, and vice versa.
- For the reliability test, if the composite reliability coefficient is above 0.7, the accurate items are reliable, and vice versa.

2.3. Data Analysis Method

This study utilizes the structural model based on partial least square to analyze the data. It happens because of the latent variables and the small sample size, 94, which is still in the required range between 30 and 100 (Ghozali 2008). Furthermore, this structural model can be got in the second equation.

$$EP = \gamma_1 \cdot OCB + \gamma_2 \cdot OC + \zeta \dots\dots\dots \text{(Equation 2)}$$

III. RESULTS & DISCUSSION

3.1. The demographic features of employees

Table 4 presents the demographic features of 94 employees joining this survey. These features contain gender, age, last formal schooling, and tenure.

- a. Based on gender, the number of men and women participating is 34 (36.17%) and 60 (63.83%).
- b. Based on age, the total employees having the age of ≤ 20 years is 11 (11.7%), 21-30 years is 12 (12.77%), 31-40 years is 33 (35.11%), 41-50 years is 21 (22.34%), >50 year is 17 (18.09%).
- c. Based on the last formal schooling, the number of employees passing senior high school is 56 (59.57%), undergraduate and vocational school is 11(11.70%), undergraduate academic school is 23 (24.47%), graduate school is 4 (4.26%).
- d. Based on tenure, the sum of employees with assignment below one year is 16 (17.02%), from one until two years is 9 (9.57%), three until five years is 19 (20.21%), five until seven years is 11 (11.70%), seven until ten years is 15 (15.96%), and above ten years is 24 (25.53%).

Table 4. Demographic features of the employees

Feature	Description	Number	The portion (%)
Gender	Man	34	36.17
	Woman	60	63.83
	Total	94	100
Age	≤ 20 years	11	11.70
	21-30 years	12	12.77
	31-40 years	33	35.11
	41-50 years	21	22.34
	> 50 year	17	18.09
	Total	94	100.00
Last formal schooling	Senior high school	56	59.57
	Undergraduate and vocational school	11	11.70
	Undergraduate academic school	23	24.47
	Graduate school	4	4.26
	Total	94	100.00
Tenure	<1 year	16	17.02
	1-3 years	9	9.57
	3-5 years	19	20.21
	5-7 years	11	11.70
	7-10 years	15	15.96
	>10 years	24	25.53
	Total	94	100.00

Source: Processed primary data

3.2. The validity and reliability test result

Table 5 consists of two panels, i.e., A and B. Panel A demonstrates the final result of the validity and reliability test for items of the dimension of organizational citizenship behavior.

- The valid altruism items are ALT1, ALT2, and ALT3 because of the loading factor of 0.762, 0.630, and 0.770, higher than 0.5. They are reliable because the composite reliability coefficient (CRC) is 0.766, higher than 0.7.
- The accurate conscientiousness items are CONS1 and CONS3 because of the loading factor of 0.814. They are reliable because CRC is 0.798, higher than 0.7.
- The usable sportsmanship items are SPORT1, SPORT2, and SPORT3 because of the loading factor of 0.743, 0.552, and 0.698. They are reliable because CRC is 0.798, higher than 0.7.
- The valid courtesy items are COURT1 and COURT3 because of the loading factor of 0.778. They are reliable because CRC is 0.754, higher than 0.7.
- The accurate civic virtue items are CV1, CV2, and CV3 because of the loading factor of 0.851, 0.710, and 0.646. They are reliable because CRC is 0.782, higher than 0.7.

Panel B demonstrates the final result of the validity and reliability test for the organizational citizenship behavior dimensions. In this panel, the loading factor of altruism, conscientiousness, sportsmanship, courtesy, civic virtue is 0.911, 0.824, 0.916, 0.708, and 0.587. Because these values are above 0.5, all the dimensions are valid. Also, the CRC for five dimensions is 0.896. Therefore, these dimensions are reliable.

Table 5. The final result of the loading factor and composite reliability coefficient related to organizational citizenship behavior

Panel A. The loading factor of items of organizational citizenship behavior dimensions			
Dimension	Item	Loading factor	CRC
Altruism	ALT1	0.762	0.766
	ALT2	0.630	
	ALT3	0.770	
Conscientiousness	CONS1	0.814	0.798
	CONS3	0.814	
Sportsmanship	SPORT1	0.743	0.706
	SPORT2	0.552	
	SPORT3	0.698	
Courtesy	COURT2	0.778	0.754
	CORTT3	0.778	
Civic Virtue	CV1	0.851	0.782
	CV2	0.710	
	CV3	0.646	
Panel B. The loading factor of the organizational citizenship behavior dimensions			
Variables	Dimension	Loading factor	CRC
Organizational Citizenship Behavior	Altruism	0.911	0.896
	Conscientiousness	0.824	
	Sportsmanship	0.916	
	Courtesy	0.708	
	Civic virtue	0.587	

Source: Modified output of Warp PLS 7.0

Table 6 presents the final test result of validity and reliability for organizational climate (OC) and employee performance (EP). The accurate OC items are OC1, OC2, OC3, OC5, OC6, and OC7. Meanwhile, all EP items are valid. These two situations happen because the loading factor of each item is higher than 0.5. Furthermore, the OC and EP items also pass the consistency test because the CRC shows 0.884 and 0.896, higher than 0.7 as the mandatory level.

Table 6. The final result of the loading factor and composite reliability coefficient of organizational climate and employee performance

Variable	Item	Loading factor	CRC
Organizational climate	OC1	0.889	0.884
	OC2	0.582	
	OC3	0.795	
	OC5	0.760	
	OC6	0.664	
	OC7	0.772	
Employee performance	EP1	0.759	0.896
	EP2	0.867	
	EP3	0.837	
	EP4	0.840	

Source: Modified output of Warp PLS 7.0

3.3. The model estimation result

Table 7 illustrates the estimation result of the structural equation model based on partial least square.

- OCB has a negative coefficient with the probability of the t-statistic of 0.216, exceeding the significance level (α) of 5%. This condition means that the negative effect is not meaningful. Therefore, the first hypothesis is rejected. In other words, OCB does not influence EP.

- OC has a positive coefficient with the probability of the t-statistic below 0.001. Because this value is lower than α of 5%, the positive effect is meaningful. Therefore, the second hypothesis declaring that the OC affects EP positively is acceptable.

Table 7. The model estimation result: The impact of Organizational Citizenship Behavior and Climate on Employee Performance

Explanatory variable	Path Coefficient	Standard error	t-statistic	Probability
OCB	-0.080	0.083	-0.964	0.216
OC	0.757	0.101	7.495	<0.001

Source: Modified output of Warp PLS 7.

3.4. Discussion

In this study, employee performance is not influenced by OCB. This situation occurs because of tenure [see Mahnaz, Mehdi, Jafar, & Abbolghasem (2013)]. In this research context, the absence of OCB on EP is caused by the employees participating in this survey have a relatively similar proportion based on their short and long working duration. It can be seen from Table 4 that the number of employees with a short working period (under one year until five years) is 44 (46.81%), and a long working period (five until above ten years) is 50 (52.19%). This condition Thus, the absent OCB effect on employee performance confirms the study of Agustiningsih et al. (2016).

Fortunately, the organizational climate has a positive effect on employee performance. According to this study, to make the work atmosphere conducive, the supervisors have to distribute the job responsibility equitably to employees, stimulate the ideas from employees, hear and the suggestions, and tolerate some employees' mistakes, encourage employees' creativity to finish the job. Hence, this positive influence supports the study of Agyemang (2013), Bhat (2014), Bhat & Bashir (2016), Raja et al. (2019), and Obeng et al. (2020).

IV. CONCLUSION

This study aims to test and analyze the impact of organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) and climate (OC) on employee performance. Furthermore, this study surveys the perception of 94 employees working in one of the pharmaceutical companies in Cimahi, West Java, Indonesia. After following the statistical analysis and discussion, this research summarizes that OCB does not influence employee performance. However, OC does with a positive sign.

There are two limitations in this study for the next interested researchers to be overwhelmed. They are the sample size and the sum of determinants of employee performance.

- Associated with the first issue, when the next researchers have the big population size, they can change the margin of error to be small, 5%, or 1%, to get more respondents to be the samples. The less a margin of error, the more representative the sample size will be.
- Associated with the second issue, the next researchers can add the other determinants of employee performance into their study model, for instance, remuneration, social adjustment, organizational support, psychological empowerment, organizational commitment, and work-life quality.

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